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Estonians' European Imaginaries: The Soviet and Pre-Soviet Legacy

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Abstract:

The article is interested in the ways that Estonia's self-perception changed in relation to Europe over the Soviet years and during the re-establishment of the independent state. More specifically, the focus is on co-articulating the "Soviet question" in relation to the "European question": in what ways did the decades of Soviet rule impact the understanding of Europe and Europeanness in Estonian national imaginaries? In such an analysis, many different factors have to be taken into account: the understanding of Europeanness before the Soviet era; the matter of the Soviet colonial matrix of power; changes within the USSR over the decades in question; the long-rooted orientalizing of Eastern Europe in West-European imaginaries, the role of Soviet state-promoted ideologies on local cultural imaginaries. In order to address this complex set of problems, it is useful to proceed from a multi-scalar understanding of social phenomena. From this perspective, Estonia's geopolitical "relocation" from the Soviet West to the European East, during the re-establishment of the Estonian republic, can be articulated as a shift in the geopolitical scale-system. In more general terms, attention to scale as a "tool for bounding space at different geographical resolutions" enables us to perceive historical conditions as complexly multiscalar. A multiscalar approach reveals how meaning-making unfolds through interaction across different scales of sociopolitical realities and imaginaries, and how in the Soviet-era Estonian SSR, local, regional, and global scales formed complex and dynamic systems of inter-dependency.

KEYWORDS: Cultural imaginaries, multiscalarity; Soviet colonial rule; aesthetics of Europeanness; imaginary geographies

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Introduction: from the West of the East, to the East of the West

In June 12, 1992, Edgar Savisaar, by then already the former head of Estonia's 1990-1992 transitional government,¹ gave a speech entitled *Eesti – Euroopa – maailm: geopolitiiline etüüd* [*Estonia – Europe – the world: a geopolitical étude*].² Savisaar opens his talk by posing Estonia's integration to Europe as an "inescapable imperative." "Our geopolitical situation over the last year has changed substantially," explains Savisaar. "We used to be the Western part of the East-European zone of influence ("sovetskii zapad"), now we are the Eastern part of the West-European zone of influence. Until 1991, in the Soviet Union, the Baltics were the generators of ideas, the explorers of new paths [teenäitaja], leaders at the fore [eestvedaja]. [...] Now we are obliged to accommodate ourselves to our new position as ones who are lagging behind [mahajääja]."³

It is hardly surprising that economists and politicians of the "times of transition" thought of Estonia's new geopolitical position and Estonia's aims and possibilities in relation to the recent past of the Soviet era. Savisaar's juxtaposition between Soviet Estonia ("a generator of ideas") and a the newly independent Estonia (which is "lagging behind") is greatly simplifying,⁴

¹ Edgar Savisaar was in power until January 1992, when he was forced to step down due to popular dissatisfaction with his government's decision to declare a state of emergency and to give government special rights for fighting the devastating economic situation. His political career began in 1987, when he, Siim Kallas, Tiit Made and Mikk Titma came up with a proposal for Estonia's economic self-management, an initiative that became one of the major political and economic movements during the Perestroika era. Savisaar remained among Estonia's leading politicians for another thirty years.

² The text of this speech, presented at the third meeting of the *Tuleviku Eesti Kongress* [The Congress of Future Estonia], was published in the November issue of the leading cultural journal *Vikerkaar*.

³ Edgar Savisaar, "Eesti – Euroopa – maailm: geopolitiiline etüüd" [1992] *Vikerkaar* 53, 53. Savisaar names Arno Käärna, Kalev Kukk, Kersten Saar and Erik Terk as participating in working out the ideas and hypotheses provided in the speech – in an academic sense, functioning as co-authors.

⁴ Politicians often have little incentive to consider more than a short-term perspective on historical developments. The relative passivity of Estonia in relation to "old Europe" must indeed have felt like a substantial change compared to Estonia's position in the perestroika-era Soviet Union. In the late 1940s and early 1950s, however, the language of "lagging behind" was used in describing the relationship of the Baltic states to the "older" parts of the Soviet Union and especially to Russia; throughout the Soviet decades, the Russians assigned themselves the title of the leading nation. In the perestroika-era discussions in the Baltics, it was precisely the inability to make local decisions locally that was often foregrounded as a major problem that needed reform. For details see Epp Annus, "The Colonizer's Day off: Colonial Subjectivities in the Soviet-Era Baltics" in Monika Albrecht (ed), *Postcolonialism and its New Discontents: Envisioning New Relations to the Colonial Past* (Routledge 2019).

yet it is hard to disagree with his basic observation of Estonia's substantially changed geopolitical position – from the West of the Soviet Union to the East of Europe. Like many others before and since, Savisaar links 'the East' with passivity and 'the West' with leadership, as if this combination was a geopolitical inevitability rather than a cultural construct.

The present article is interested in the ways that Estonia's self-perception has changed in relation to Estonians' European imaginaries. More specifically, the focus is on co-articulating the "Soviet question" in relation to the "European question": in what ways did the decades of Soviet rule impact the understanding of Europe and Europeanness in Estonian national imaginaries? In such an analysis, different factors have to be taken into account: the understanding of Europeanness before the Soviet era; the matter of the Soviet colonial matrix of power; changes within the USSR over the decades in question; the long-rooted orientalizing of Eastern Europe in West-European imaginaries, the role of Soviet state-promoted ideologies on local cultural imaginaries. The "Soviet question", as this exploration will show, was never solely a question about the Soviet impact, but rather about how the intertwining of Soviet era sociopolitical realities with pre-Soviet value-systems produced complex and to some extent competing geographies of belonging.

In order to address this complex set of problems, it is useful to proceed from a *multiscalar understanding of social phenomena*. From this perspective, Estonia's geopolitical "relocation" from the Soviet West to the European East, occasioned by the re-establishment of the Estonian republic, can be articulated as a shift in the geopolitical scale-system. In more general terms, attention to scale as a "tool for bounding space at different geographical resolutions"⁵ enables us to perceive historical conditions as complexly multiscalar. A multiscalar approach reveals how meaning-making unfolds through interaction across different scales of sociopolitical realities and imaginaries, and how in the Soviet-era Estonian SSR, local, regional, and global scales formed complex and dynamic systems of inter-dependency.

The collapse of the Soviet Union and the re-establishment of the Estonian Republic brought about substantial changes at all levels of social and political existence. During the decades of the Estonian SSR, the general category of "the West" (not "Europe") had provided a cultural counterpoint to "Sovietness," and the scale of Europeanness was significantly

⁵ Andrew Herod and Melissa W Wright, "Placing Scale: An Introduction" in Andrew Herod and Melissa W Wright (eds), *Geographies of power: Placing scale* (Blackwell 2002) 6.

deactivated. At the same time, analysis does reveals the hazy category of a tacit, internalized Europeanness, something perceivable mostly in contrast with certain imaginaries of Russianness. This tacit Europeanness included class and cultural competency and knowledge of European cultural traditions, yet it was only weakly (if at all) connected to then-current cultural developments in Europe. It lacked a dialogical dimension. In the early post-Soviet years, the newly rescaled relationship to Europe relied on longstanding imaginaries, yet it also – as Edgar Savisaar’s 1992 speech attests – went through the shock of Estonia “becoming the East.” The new situation (re)activated the concept of Europe as an imperative category and a point of reference for both political and cultural frameworks.

This paper will first articulate the theoretical framework of cultural imaginaries and multiscalar thinking, and then proceed to analyse the scalar cultural logic of the Soviet era, with a focus on the “question of Europe.” The last section will summarize the consequences following from the reestablishment of Estonian independence. The complexities of the Soviet decades are, of course, considerable; the present essay will concentrate on the late Soviet period, from the 1960s to the mid-1980s. The essay will focus on the Estonian-speaking cultural zone: while such a choice is necessitated by the scarcity of data concerning European imaginaries among other population groups in Soviet and early post-Soviet Estonia, it also conveys the logic of the present project. By the 2020s, Russophone populations have become to a significant extent integrated within Estonia’s political and cultural sphere, yet during the early post-Soviet period, when Estonia’s policies of integration with Europe were formulated, Russophone populations participated in this process only marginally.

Theoretical framework: cultural imaginaries and their role in identity-production

To understand sociocultural processes during periods of (semi-)authoritarian rule, the *distinction between state policies and cultural imaginaries* helps to avoid simplifying arguments about mass-level “ideological brain-washing” or an organized state-production of certain kinds of personality-types, leading to uncritical categorizations such as *homo sovieticus*.⁶ State ideology and state policies are one factor, but not the only factor, contributing to people’s views and behaviours – while this premise is taken for granted in analyses of democratic societies, it is

⁶ For a critique of the label “*homo sovieticus*”, see Gulnaz Sharafutdinova, “Was There a ‘Simple Soviet’ Person? Debating the Politics and Sociology of ‘Homo Sovieticus’” (2019) 78 *Slavic Review* 173.

too often overlooked in writings about the former Socialist bloc. Soviet rule was firmly established in the Baltics only at the end of the 1940s⁷ and its heyday lasted barely forty years. During these decades, people's thoughts and value-systems continued to include ideas, values, and beliefs from the pre-Soviet era. These became mixed with state-imposed ideologies and were additionally impacted by a large variety of images and narratives from cultural zones beyond the Soviet sphere – existentialist writings by Albert Camus were widely read, popular North-American TV serials (Dallas, for example) were available in northern Estonia by way of Finnish broadcasting, Eastern religious thought and global environmental discussions made their mark. The notion of “cultural imaginaries” is useful in keeping a distinction between the ideological networks of institutionalized power and the popular circulation of ideas. This distinction is, of course, partial, as both are hazy and shifting categories which necessarily also influence each other. Nevertheless, identifiable kernels remain: a canonical speech by Lenin and the textbook of the Communist Party share little in common with Beatles' songs, Disney comics, nineteenth-century Estonian patriotic poetry, and a grandmother's stories about life in the times of an independent Estonia – but they all circulated and comingled together in the Estonian cultural space.

I use the term “cultural imaginaries” to designate diverse, multiscalar, hazy, ever-changing sets of images, ideas, and values that are accepted by the general population in any given period and thus form a tacit self-knowledge of that society. In this field, communal identity is produced metonymically, foregrounding certain parts at the expense of others – not everyone's voice is heard at every moment.⁸ Us–them figurations function as important formal categories that condition cultural imaginaries – thus one of the questions in this investigation is whether and

⁷ In the Estonian SSR, the first post-war years are considered the “post-Estonian period.” The mass deportations of 1949 and the 8th plenum of the Central Committee of the Estonian C(b)P in 1950 designate the end of the “post-Estonian period” and the firm establishment of Soviet rule. Tiiu Kreegipuu, “Eesti kultuurielu sovetiseerimine: Nõukogude kultuuripoliitika eesmärgid ja institutsionaalne raamistik aastatel 1944-1954” in Tõnu Tannberg (ed), *Tõnu Tannberg (ed), Eesti NSV aastatel 1940-1953: sovetiseerimise mehhanismid ja tagajärjed Nõukogude Liidu ja Ida-Euroopa arengute kontekstis. Eesti Ajalooarhiivi Toimetised 15 (22)* (Eesti Ajalooarhiiv 2007) 356–358. Notably, after Stalin died in March 1953, the system already started to ease its grip. While the late 1960s saw a new tightening of regime control, from 1986 (in Estonia, from 1987) the Soviet regime once again started to loosen its grip – and never recovered it again before the collapse of the whole system.

⁸ Epp Annus, “A Post-Soviet Eco-Digital Nation? Metonymic Processes of Nation-Building and Estonia's High-Tech Dreams in the 2010s” (2022) 36 *East European Politics and Societies* 399.

under what conditions Europe was considered as “us.” Imaginaries form thematic clusters, which occasionally get condensed into core images that attain symbolic value and start to function metaphorically. Such core images become kernels for the signification of national identity – in Estonia, these have included the pillars of Tartu University, the medieval towers of Tallinn, junipers on the island of Saaremaa, Haapsalu castle, imagery from nineteenth-century romantic poetry, and much more. Notably, these core images have historic depth – they carry the sense of “having been there” for centuries, if not for thousands of years. Presentist imaginaries about social existence in any given era are bound together with a pre-existing fabric of interconnected values, ideas, and images.

The concept of cultural imaginaries is related to Charles Taylor’s concept of the “social imaginary,” which Taylor articulated as “the ways people imagine their social existence, how they fit together with others, how things go on between them and their fellows, the expectations that are normally met, and the deeper normative notions and images that underlie these expectations.”⁹ Cultural and social imaginaries are to a significant extent overlapping concepts, and the “political imaginary” – including “constitutional imaginary” – belongs to the same set. For Taylor, “social imaginary” describes the common ground of a particular moment in the existence of a society; as Jiří Příbáň notes, this concept puts an emphasis on “the symbolic system of images and normative self-descriptions of society as the moral and meaningful unit.”¹⁰ My own use of “cultural imaginaries” includes *both* the present-era social and political imaginaries in a given culture *and* an emphasis on cultural continuity; this term also allows scholars to take account of the role of cultural artefacts – in architecture, visual arts, literature, film – in shaping and preserving shared imaginaries. I have elsewhere articulated the threefold temporality of cultural imaginaries: “Cultural imaginaries consist of the shared images and narratives of the past, patterns of behavior for the present, and visions for the national future that together shape the self-conception of the community.”¹¹ In historical terms, the logic of shared imaginaries reflects larger global processes of growing diversification: over the last decades, the

⁹ Charles Taylor, *Modern Social Imaginaries* (Duke University Press 2004) 23.

¹⁰ Jiří Příbáň, “Constitutional Imaginaries and Legitimation: On Potentia, Potestas, and Auctoritas in Societal Constitutionalism” (2018) 45 *Journal of Law and Society* S30, S37.

¹¹ Epp Annus, *Soviet Postcolonial Studies: A View from the Western Borderlands* (Routledge 2018) 173.

role of nationally shared imaginaries has shrunk substantially, yet in the Soviet era, and during the first post-Soviet decade, their role was considerable.

Accessing something that is not fixed and not even fully articulated in a given culture will, of course, pose a challenge for scholars. Cultural imaginaries can be traced in life stories, in diaries, memoirs, and through performing interviews – all of which raise questions about the unreliability of memory, selective remembering techniques, and narrative strategies. The lack of “eventness” of the shared cultural common ground poses additional problems: the common cultural elements might be taken for granted to such an extent that they are not thematized in life stories. Media, fiction and film thus become valuable gateways to era-specific imaginaries, partly due to the sheer volume of such sources, which makes it possible to detect repeating patterns. However, reliable research into era-specific imaginaries is perhaps best achieved through comparative methods which combine and compare the aforementioned sources.

Cultural imaginaries – like any other cultural phenomenon – can be analysed at different levels of generalization and focus. Imaginaries can be analysed across *different scales* – we might talk of imaginaries with a transnational spread, or focus on national imaginaries, imaginaries that can typically be found within a nation-state. *National imaginaries* may well internalize transcultural ideas and practices – and reimagine them as specific to a given national culture.

In analysing the constitution of shared imaginaries, a pluriscalar approach allows us to observe the multiplicity of processes involved in meaning-making. The next section will offer a short introduction to scalar analysis and then delineate the basic outline of this threefold cultural logic, in order to then locate the European imaginaries within this network of constitutive power-relations.

Pluriscalarity in the sociopolitical context of the Soviet Union as the ground for European imaginaries

In principle, there are countless ways to scale reality: in world-systems theory, the global world functions as the dominant scale; in phenomenological approaches, the human body and its experience provides the primary access to the world. Political geographers have held debates about the ontological status of scales, asking if scale is “a material thing” or else an arbitrary,

socially produced “mental device which allows us to make sense of our existence.”¹² Scale-systems have been envisioned in different ways, as forming nested systems, or concentric ones, or ladder-type hierarchies or, following Bruno Latour, as networks without clear structure and subordinations.¹³ A “trilogy of geographical scales” is often used: a three-scale analysis distinguishes between international or global, national or state-scale, and intra-national scales.¹⁴

In sociohistorical analyses, the nation-state or a particular region is often taken as the central focus, leading to classification of scales as “interior” and “exterior” with respect to the nation-state.¹⁵ For a nation-state, the state-level forms the “here and now” of the world, with other layers forming hierarchical constellations and standing in relation to this primary ground. Edgar Savisaar’s 1992 speech, introduced at the start of this paper, chose an international relations approach, in which three basic scales – Estonia, Europe, and the world – were used to analyse smaller national and regional units, including different European countries, the Baltic states, Russia, China and more.

For present purposes it is necessary to distinguish between cultural imaginaries and sociopolitical conditions. While scalar hierarchies tend to be dominated by sociopolitical facts (such as belonging to a union of states or being a part of an empire), cultural imaginaries question and complicate such sociopolitical realities and create alternative geographies of belonging. Our questions include: to what extent were European imaginaries in the Soviet era tied to pre-existing culture-specific imaginaries, and to what extent did they reflect specific sociopolitical conditions? Which scales become foregrounded and which ones recede? How do scalar hierarchies organize the cultural distribution of meanings and values? Even when one limits the main focus to just a single scale – the nation-scale and its European imaginaries in the

¹² Herod and Wright (n 5) 5.

¹³ Andrew Herod, *Scale* (Routledge 2010) 15, 48–52.

¹⁴ Colin Flint and Peter J Taylor, *Political Geography: World-Economy, Nation-State and Locality* (Routledge 2018) 35.

¹⁵ Lauristin and Vihalemm explain such an agenda: “When speaking of ‘external factors,’ we mean those influences emanating from the presence of international, intersocietal and intercultural forces in a given society, whereas ‘internal factors’ refers to the mutual interrelations of values and social structure (social classes, ethnic groups, generations, gender groups, etc.) as they are institutionalized in a given society.” Marju Lauristin and Peeter Vihalemm, “The Political Agenda During Different Periods of Estonian Transformation: External and Internal Factors” (2009) 40 *Journal of Baltic Studies* 1, 2.

present case – this scale assumes its full meaning only in the context of the other scalar hierarchies of the era.

Tensions and autonomies – the all-USSR scale *versus* the SSR scale

In the Soviet Union, tensions frequently arose between the interests of the central governing bodies and those of non-Russian republics. The *all-Union (the USSR-level) scale* foregrounded the USSR as a whole, but also singled out the capital city Moscow and the city of Leningrad as of privileged importance, as these housed major institutional headquarters and other ideologically crucial centres, and also fulfilled the function of showcasing Soviet life. From an all-Soviet perspective, non-Russian republic-levels¹⁶ and lower-level scales (regional units) served to implement all-Soviet aims and to accommodate all-Union enterprises. In a centrally regulated economy, all localities fed into the all-Union economic system.¹⁷ The all-Union scale as such consisted of a paradox: if it existed only as a sum of all republics, yet did not represent the interests of the republics, then what interests did it represent? What looks like the paradox of an empty signifier was in actuality a colonial-style system of power occasionally tempered by a socialist reticence with respect to extreme forms of exploitation.¹⁸

At the *scale of the Estonian SSR*, local leadership would make an effort to foreground republic-level interests over the Union-scale, but local leaders were under Union-level supervision and had to constantly check their decision-making against the written and unwritten expectations of the centre.¹⁹ Moreover in economic terms, within the territory of the republics,

¹⁶ The all-Union scale was in an ambiguous relation to the Russian SFSR: in some respects, the two scales merged, as the capital of the Russian SFSR was also the capital of the USSR, a separate Communist Party did not exist in the RSFSR until 1990, and the Russian nation was undoubtedly the ideological leader in the USSR. Even though in terms of geopolitical scalarity the RSFSR was a separate entity *within* the USSR, among Russians, the imaginary of the Soviet Union as one great homeland was widely internalized – a view that has led Russia to its present-day “imperial hangover” and to new military annexations in the years after the collapse of the USSR.

¹⁷ Some shorter periods, however, allowed for greater economic autonomy.

¹⁸ Concerning the colonial matrix of power within the Soviet Union see Annus, *Soviet Postcolonial Studies: A View from the Western Borderlands* (n 11); Epp Annus (ed), *Coloniality, Nationality, Modernity: A Postcolonial View on Baltic Cultures under Soviet Rule* (Routledge 2018).

¹⁹ For the republic-level Central Committee of the Communist Party, the main decision-making organ, the first secretary (that is, the leader of the party and of the republic) would be chosen under strict supervision from Moscow; the second secretary was always non-local and directly appointed by Moscow. In case of

one had to deal with all-Union and mixed union-republic level industries, where in both cases the republic-level leaders had little sway.²⁰ This created a typical colonial situation, where locals suffered the ecological consequences of industries over which they had little or no control. Similarly, the republics quartered all-Union military units and border guards, which, again, were beyond the jurisdiction of local decision making. Thus the republic scale *was not quite republic level* – rather, it was overwritten by the all-Union matrix of power. Notably, there were whole towns that belonged to the Union-level and were closed to visitors without special permission – Sillamäe (with its uranium-processing plant) and Paldiski (a military town), for example, were effectively non-Estonian sites within Estonia. At both the SSR-level and the USSR-level scaled systems, a clear internal-external division was missing: from the republic-level perspective, the SSR- and USSR-levels were thoroughly entwined, and for the Union-level, the Eastern bloc further functioned as its logical extension.

While in economic and sociopolitical terms the Estonian SSR was strongly dependent on all-USSR decisionmaking, Estonians' cultural imaginaries sustained some autonomy from sociopolitical realities. In cultural imaginaries, tradition, cultural memory, and one's personal, affective relationship to concrete surroundings all play a role, while the political dissatisfactions of any present situation can be partially compensated by cultural memory. The result is a “messy scalarity,” a hazy and flexible network of images, ideas, and values. As we will see in the next section, both “Europe” and “the West” had a role to play there.

The changing location of Europe

In the **all-Soviet scale** of the postwar era, *Europe as a relatively coherent entity disappeared*; instead, Europe was split into the Soviet zone of influence and capitalist Western Europe. Eastern Europe, subject to guidance from Moscow, functioned as an extension of the Soviet sphere, while Western Europe became inaccessible to the general Soviet citizenry.

the Estonian SSR, the first secretaries Johannes Käbin (1950 – 1978) and Karl Vaino (1978 – 1988) had both grown up in Russia and were sent to Estonia on the orders of the all-Union Communist Party.

²⁰ There were three classifications for Soviet-era industrial enterprises: ‘All-Union’ (under the direct control of Moscow), ‘Union-Republic’ (in which Moscow played the dominant role), and those under ‘Republic’ control. The role of local administration differed during different periods of the Soviet era; after the heavily centralized Stalinist era, more power devolved to the republics; with the end of the Khrushchev Thaw, a new wave of centralization took place.

It is worth noting that the early Soviet Union had been significantly better connected to Europe: figures like Vladimir Mayakovsky could spend extended periods in Paris, Ilya Ehrenburg would actively contribute to Soviet press while living in Paris, Soviet scientists published in Western journals and interacted with Western colleagues. Germany, of course, was an important partner for the USSR in the interwar period, with many major German companies maintaining some presence there.²¹ This sustained connectedness was partially due to weaknesses in the state of the USSR in its early history; it was only later on that scientific and military collaboration with the Germans and with the rest of the world came to be regarded with great suspicion by Stalin, inspiring trials and persecutions.

In the Khrushchev era, networks of interaction were developed anew – delegations of architects, for example, traveled to Scandinavia and to Western Europe, to learn about mass-scale urban planning in line with new factory-assembled construction methods.²² Yet westward travel from the Socialist bloc remained open only for a limited number of political, cultural, and scientific or economic elites, and was a complex undertaking with onerous limitations.

From sociopolitics to cultural imaginaries

In the popular imagination, too, Europe as a functional category weakened as the “iron curtain” split Europe in two. Imaginary “Europeanness” could function only as a *relative category*, not as an entity with determinate boundaries – places could be more or less European. Europeanness in this context tended to be associated with *urban culture*: Bulgaria and Poland were considered somewhat less European than Prague, Budapest or Dresden, and unattainable Paris and London crowned the popular hierarchy.²³

If Soviet-era Eastern Europe was not regarded as fully European, Western Europe as a category failed in its own way to secure a clearly defined identity. In lieu of “Europe,” the “West” was the signifier of choice for the imaginary better world beyond the confines of the

²¹ Ian Ona Johnson, *Faustian Bargain: The Soviet-German Partnership and the Origins of the Second World War* (Oxford University Press 2021).

²² Marija Drėmaitė, *Baltic Modernism: Architecture and Housing in Soviet Lithuania* (DOM Publishers 2017).

²³ Even as personal correspondences with the “outside world” became possible once again in the late Soviet era, without a support of the socio-political level, these epistolary encounters of (semi-) intimate scale did not become generalized into ideas of Europe. One would not say, for example, I received a package from Europe – no, the package came from my aunt or from Sweden.

Soviet borders. Marju Lauristin has suggested that the categories of West and Europe were “virtually synonymous,”²⁴ yet both popular culture and the general Cold War framework suggest otherwise. The late Soviet-era category of “the West” also included American culture – indeed arguably the U.S. was regarded as the preeminent constituent of “the West.”²⁵ Europe as a category was thus *doubly dispersed*: it was subsumed within the larger category of the West under American dominance and it was zoned into sites that were either more or less European.²⁶

The location of Europe from the Estonian perspective: sociopolitical realities

For Estonians, Soviet-era sociopolitical realities differed vastly from those in pre-Soviet times. The prewar Estonian Republic had been situated in what retrospectively looked like a clearly defined system of nested sociopolitical scalarity: Estonia – Europe – the world. This system was interwoven by various political, economic and cultural networks.

The Soviet colonial matrix of power dismantled historical ties that had organized the Baltic sea region and had linked Estonia with other European countries. Colonial-style centre-periphery relations made it nearly impossible for the Soviet borderlands (including the Estonian SSR) to sustain or develop direct connections with institutions or businesses outside the USSR. Prior to the Soviet annexation, geographical and linguistic proximity with Finland had facilitated close, even intimate relations between Estonians and Finns – connections included business and politics, of course, but also ties of love and friendship.²⁷ With the new era, political, economic and cultural interactions with the world outside the USSR had to be routed through Moscow; in such instances, republic-level interests were secondary and personal connections unsustainable. This was a particularly suggestive example of the colonial matrix of control exerted by the

²⁴ Marju Lauristin, “The European Public Sphere and the Social Imaginary of the ‘New Europe’” (2007) 22 *European Journal of Communication* 397, 398.

²⁵ Examples include a widespread fascination with the TV serial *Dallas*, the popularity of Micky-Mouse and Donald comic books, and American popular music.

²⁶ Mapping of Europeanness also privileged cities over countries: Prague would thus be associated with stronger Europeanness than Czechoslovakia.

²⁷ The late nineteenth-century and the early twentieth-century history of Estonian culture is the story of a deep connectedness with Finland. Friedebert Tuglas, a classic Estonian author, hid in Finland from Tsarist authorities; Marie Under, perhaps the most celebrated Estonian poet of all time, loved to vacation in Finland; Aino Kallas, the most celebrated pre-war Finnish female writer, married an Estonian and lived mostly in Estonia until its Soviet annexation.

USSR, as regards the Estonian SSR: the disruption and rerouting of former economic and cultural ties that had formerly bound Estonia closely with Finland and other European countries.²⁸ As a result, not only did Estonia cease to be a political and economic entity which could interact with the rest of the world in pursuit of its own interests, the whole sociocultural sphere was permeated with such limitations: only on rare occasions could Estonian musicians participate in major international competitions outside the Soviet Union,²⁹ foreign films reached Estonian audiences only after being selected, cut, censored and dubbed in Russia, with Estonian subtitles composed according to the Russian dubbing, and without access to the original.³⁰ Cultural exchanges of the late Soviet years, such as Estonian theatre performances in Finland and Finnish theatre troupes' visits to Estonia could not bypass Moscow.³¹ Soviet tourist groups did occasionally include members of the Estonian Soviet elite, but the company as a whole would in such cases be identified as Soviet.³² The “iron curtain” hid the borderlands more profoundly than it hid the Soviet centre: for most of the rest of the world, the Soviet Union became equated with Russia.

Given the structural hindrance suffered by Estonian scientists and artists seeking contact with the outside world, it was, paradoxically, Leningrad and (to a lesser extent) Moscow that started to function as *access points to Europe* – these were the cities one could visit to gain access to information, knowledge, and high art.³³ In the Russian centres, a certain limited

²⁸ Annus, *Soviet Postcolonial Studies: A View from the Western Borderlands* (n 11).

²⁹ Anu Kõlar, *Interpretatsioonikunst ja kontserdielu sulaperioodil*. Forthcoming.

³⁰ For film clubs, however, circulation might work differently. Once Helsinki-Tallinn ferry traffic was opened in the 1960s, it became one of the channels through which club-films could acquire films. These were shown with synchronous translation, in TPI, with two professional translators covering ten languages; in Tartu, students were also used. Tiina Hoffmann, “La Traduction cinématographique en Estonie soviétique: Contextes, pratiques et acteurs” (University of Tartu, 2021).

³¹ Luule Epner, “Soome dramaturgia Nõukogude Eesti teatrilaval” [2019] *Keel ja Kirjandus* 849–867, 852–853.

³² Soviet elites did indeed travel around. When, in 1979, a group of 22 Estonians toured Canada and the USA, for the writer Aadu Hint it was already his fourth visit to Canada. Ene Maremäe, “Kolm nädalat Ameerika mandril” *Sirp ja Vasar* (December 31, 1976) 4, 12–4.

³³ The role of Leningrad and Moscow is well documented in life-writing: sources include diaries by the writer Vaino Vahing, several interviews with the artist Tõnis Vint, published recollections by the art historian Krista Kodres, life stories in the volumes of *Eesti elulood*, memoirs by the composer Veljo Tormis and more. Literary examples include Aili Paju’s novel *Merkuuri tütar*; Mats Traat’s novel *Inger*, and short stories by Maimu Berg.

openness was restored after the period of Stalinist excess, and research budgets were by far more generous than those disbursed in the borderlands. Leading Russian academic centres could order scientific journals published in the West and thus open up access to global knowledge production. Estonian scholars and intellectuals would visit libraries in Leningrad and Moscow to browse through Western scholarly and cultural journals that were indispensable for their work: the library at the Hermitage, for example, included exhibition catalogues and art journals that never reached Estonian libraries.³⁴ International artists would more likely visit Moscow and Leningrad than Tallinn; similarly, the occasional exhibitions of Western art (such as the Picasso exhibition in 1956) were shown in Moscow and Leningrad and nowhere else.³⁵ The 6th World Festival of Youth and Students in Moscow 1957, which included many Western participants, gave many visiting Estonians inspiring encounters with the contemporary Western cultural sphere.³⁶ There were historical roots to this phenomenon: St Petersburg, historically Estonia's closest major European city, had long functioned for Estonians as an access point to Europe. During the late Tsarist era, this city functioned for many cultural figures (Johann Köler, Miina Härma) as a place to acquire (typically German-style) education or to find fulfilling employment.³⁷

The Europeanness of Russia more broadly, however, had also been repeatedly contested over different periods by Russian cultural elites themselves – most famously by Pyotr Chaadayev in his *First Philosophical Letter* (1829): the author argued that Russians had “bestowed not even a single idea upon the fund of human ideas, contributed nothing to the progress of the human

³⁴ Krista Kodres, “The Soviet West? Shifting Boundaries of Estonian Culturescape” in Natalya Zlydneva (ed), *At the Crossroads of the East and the West: the Problems of Borderzone in Russian and Central European Cultures* (Institut Slavovedeniya, Rossiiskaya Akademiya Nauk 2021) 438.

³⁵ Maria Dmitreva, “The Riddle of Modernism in the Art Historical Discourse of the Thaw” in Krista Kodres, Kristina Jõekalda and Michaela Marek (eds), *A Socialist Realist History: Writing Art History in the Postwar decades* (Böhlau 2019).

³⁶ Kädi Talvoja has documented the impact of the festival for emerging Estonian avant-garde movements in the visual arts. Kädi Talvoja, *Karm stiil Eesti kunstiajalookirjutuse kontekstis. Severe Style in the Context of Estonian Art History Writing. Dissertationes Academiae Artium Estoniae 27* (Eesti Kunstiakadeemia 2019).

³⁷ Annus, *Soviet Postcolonial Studies: A View from the Western Borderlands* (n 11) 132; Jaan Ross, “Eestlaste Kultuurielu Peterburis” *Sirp* (November 19, 2021).

spirit.”³⁸ Madina Tlostanova and Vyacheslav Morozov³⁹ have used the notion of “Russia’s subaltern empire” (Morozov) or the “quasi-Western subaltern Russian Empire” (Tlostanova)⁴⁰ to describe Russia’s historical struggle with its subalternity or its feeling of secondariness with regard to other major European powers.⁴¹ For visiting Estonians, similarly, the experience of visiting Leningrad and Moscow often included a high degree of ambivalence.

The aesthetics of Europeanness: continuities in cultural imaginaries across political regime changes

The double dispersal of Europe – its split into two and its subsumption within the larger category of the “West” – could not erase Europe from Estonian cultural imaginaries. The slowness, inertia, and multiplicity of cultural processes guarantees the preservation of traces of “what used to be” throughout periods increasingly dominated by new sets of values and ideas. An annexation or a revolution can change the sociopolitical order of a state or a territory within a period of a few years, yet the process of changing collectively shared cultural understandings might well take decades and may only ever be partially successful. At a personal and regional level, continuity is also sustained by material culture and by natural environment: the same physical items, similar architectural structures, and kindred topographical features support the sense of continuity or permanence.

After the Soviet takeover, the new regime contended against earlier cultural traditions and values and created new hybrid imaginaries, yet supposedly displaced images and values and tropes persisted. Key cultural works and events of various kind, notably those attached to school curricula, continued to function as resources for cultural continuity.⁴² The Soviet state could not

³⁸ English translation is from Nicholas V. Riasanovsky, *The Image of Peter the Great in Russian History and Thought* (Oxford University Press 1992) 99.

³⁹ Morozov considers the “the dialectic of the subaltern and the imperial” as a source of ontological insecurity in present-day Russia. Viatcheslav Morozov, *Russia’s Postcolonial Identity: A Subaltern Empire in a Eurocentric World* (Palgrave Macmillan 2015) 104.

⁴⁰ Madina Tlostanova, *Gender Epistemologies and Eurasian Borderlands* (Palgrave Macmillan 2010) 64.

⁴¹ Annus, *Soviet Postcolonial Studies: A View from the Western Borderlands* (n 11) 129.

⁴² As the Soviet Union made no effort to encourage new settlers to become acquainted with the local cultural sphere, in the Estonian SSR there remained strong contrasts between ethnic Estonians and Russophone Soviet-era settlers – contrasts that diminished somewhat over the Soviet decades, due to similar everyday material circumstances. Research from the 1990s reveals clear differences in the self-identities of ethnic

impose a wholesale rejection of major cultural developments before the Soviet era, so much of the pre-Soviet Estonian cultural canon was appropriated into the Soviet ideological framework and continued its cultural circulation. During the Soviet era, Estonian school curricula included nineteenth-century patriotic songs and poems, but also classic twentieth-century novels that had defined a pre-Soviet national consciousness.⁴³ For the imaginaries about Estonia's situatedness vis-à-vis Europe, the early twentieth-century Noor-Eesti (Young Estonia) movement played a special role.

The Noor-Eesti movement, founded in 1905, earned its place in the Estonian cultural canon for its Nietzschean programme of radical cultural innovation.⁴⁴ Its young members decisively rejected the German and Russian influences that had been dominant in nineteenth-century Estonian culture, instead they valorised Scandinavian and Romance cultures.⁴⁵ Such nuances became lost in popular imaginaries, however, and Noor-Eesti became synonymous with the aspiration toward Europeanness in general. In its 1905 manifesto *Noorte püüded* [*The Strivings of Young People*], the movement declared that its mission was “to seek those aims and forms, to which we are guided, from one direction, by the spirit of our nation and the natural capacities and requirements of our nation, and, from the other direction, by European culture.”⁴⁶ The same text also supplied the slogan “Let’s be Estonians, but let’s also become Europeans!”

Estonian and Soviet-era settlers and their children – a difference that started to diminish over the course of the 1990s.

⁴³ The Soviet era rhetoric presented nineteenth-century nation-building as resistance to Baltic German landlords and thus established linkages with Soviet discourse of its arch-enemy, the Germans – in Soviet parlance as “exploiters of the toiling masses”.

⁴⁴ Epp Annus, “Noorte püüded ja rõõmus ajalugu: Gustav Suits ja Friedrich Nietzsche” [2005] *Keel ja Kirjandus* 526.

⁴⁵ Virve Sarapik, “Young Estonia and The Early Twentieth-Century Cultural Utopias” (2014) 45 *Journal of Baltic Studies* 207, 208.

⁴⁶ “Meie tahame otsida neid sihtisid ja wormisid, millede juurde meid ühest küljest meie oma rahwa waim, meie rahwa loomulikud omadused ja wajadused, teiselt poolt europaline kultur juhatab.” Gustav Suits [“Noor Eesti” toim], ‘Noorte püüded. Üksikud mõtted meie oleviku kohta’, *Noor-Eesti I* (Kirjanduse Sõprade kirjastus 1905) 19.

and the short catch-phrase “More culture! More European-style culture!”⁴⁷ ⁴⁸ The formulaic structure of these proclamations made their dissemination all the easier.

The Noor-Eesti movement was treated critically during the period of high Stalinism,⁴⁹ but the Khrushchev era re-established its cultural importance. Somewhat paradoxically, the Noor-Eesti slogan found its way into Soviet school curricula: it was helpful that Noor-Eesti leaders had been excited about the 1905 revolution, since this positioned them on the “right” side of history.⁵⁰ Voldemar Miller could write in the weekly *Sirp ja Vasar*, in 1970: “The Noor-Eesti movement developed under the direct impact of the 1905-1906 revolution, their slogan was ‘Let’s be Estonians, but let’s also become Europeans!’ The Noor-Eesti movement turned into an important landmark (verstapost) in the development of the aesthetic view of Estonians, in their Europeanization.”⁵¹ And Mai Levin, in 1979, stressed in the same weekly newspaper the role of Noor-Eesti in the context of its era, while pointing to the combination of the European and the national: “at this stage of the development of national culture, a deeper investment in European culture was both unavoidable and necessary, much as the demand for a national subject matter in art was objectively conditioned.”⁵²

For Noor-Eesti, *Europeanness was an aesthetic, not a political category* – this was an important precondition for the adoption of their slogan in the Soviet era. In cultural circulation, the Noor-Eesti declaration acquired a life of its own, however, partly independent of its original historical context. A colorful example is provided in Herbert Vainu’s vulgar-Soviet lampoon of a typical member of Soviet Estonia’s economic elite:

If he hasn't remembered anything else from “Noor-Eesti” in his school years, then at least he remembers the figurative slogan "Let's be Estonians, but let's also become

⁴⁷ *ibid* 17.

⁴⁸ This short version, now part of Estonian imaginaries, redacts an intervening sentence. The original reads: “And our call is: More culture! This is the first condition of all aspirations and efforts for liberation. More European-style culture!” *ibid.* 17.

⁴⁹ The historian Ea Jansen records that, in 1950, the Stalinist functionary Max Laosson called Noor-Eesti “a marriage between a syphilitic French lady and an Estonian peasant.” Marika Mikli and Ea Jansen, “Vestlus Ea Janseniga” [1995] *Vikerkaar* 153, 155.

⁵⁰ Sarapik (n 46) 208.

⁵¹ Voldemar Miller, “Raamat Eesti Kultuuriloos” *Sirp ja Vasar* (September 18, 1970) 4,6 6.

⁵² Mai Levin, “Aleksander Promet” *Sirp ja Vasar* (October 19, 1979) 8.

Europeans!" And he proves that he is both – welcome in Rannamõisa's "Rannapiiga,"⁵³ but not a gaping fool at a restaurant in Helsinki or on Place Pigalle – and, as a cultured person, he will also go to the Grand Opera.⁵⁴

“Kui tal koolipõlves muud “Noor-Eestist” pole meelde jäänud, siis vähemalt kujundlik loosung “Olgem eestlased, aga saagem ka eurooplasteks!” Ja ta tõestab, et ta on see ja teine – omainimene Rannamõisa “Rannapiigas”, ei jää tolaks Helsinki ravintola’s ega Place Pigalle’il ja kultuuriinimesena käib ka Grand Opera’s ära.”

Such an easy appropriation suggests that, by the late Soviet era, the Noor-Eesti dictum had become a commonplace in Estonia’s cultural self-identification. It had engraved itself as a cultural imaginary with historic depth, one of those core ideas with a special symbolic value that play a significant role in building and sustaining national identity. Notably, this imaginary figured the future of Estonian culture as securely bound together with that of Europe.

Yet even as Noor-Eesti foregrounded the necessity of close relations with Scandinavian and Romance cultural spheres, its central statement is directed elsewhere: it is the acknowledgement of a lack. For Noor-Eesti, Estonian Europeanness was not a given, but rather an aim and a direction. Noor-Eesti’s leading voices coupled their European aspirations with criticism of the “overly Germanic” Estonian culture of their era. In its original context, the slogan hardly offered an easy positive identification with Europe, yet in the Soviet context, it nevertheless served to affirm Estonia’s imaginary affiliation with Europe – Noor-Eesti members had, after all, freely traveled all over Europe. The temporal distance from Noor-Eesti times was necessary for their call to crystallize into a symbolic gesture, and the historic distance was further accentuated by the cultural rupture of the Soviet annexation. I have elsewhere described such a situation through the double dialectics of nostalgia and colonial rupture: “first, the colonial split initiated a discourse of national nostalgia; and second, the nostalgic lens further intensified the colonial conflict.”⁵⁵ The mere fact of the Soviet annexation guaranteed the Noor-Eesti slogan a special place in national imaginaries.

⁵³ A popular modern restaurant on the outskirts of Tallinn.

⁵⁴ Herbert Vainu, “Renessansist Maarjamaal” *Sirp ja Vasar* (1976) 3,10 10.

⁵⁵ Annus, *Soviet Postcolonial Studies: A View from the Western Borderlands* (n 11) 10.

Binarisms in everyday cultural imaginaries: Europe and Russia

In addition to the persistence and deepening of various pre-Soviet cultural aspirations, era-specific factors – especially those linked to the Soviet-era colonial conflict – also contributed to the cultural imaginary of Estonia’s Europeanness. The “Soviet gaze” classed the *Pribaltika* as the “Soviet West” and thus supported local self-understandings as being more Western than the rest of the USSR. Examples abound: Elena Zubkova even opens her monograph *Pribaltika i Kreml’ (The Baltics and the Kremlin)* with a recollection of the *Soviet Pribaltika* enjoying a special significance for those living in the USSR.⁵⁶ Art curator Alla Rosenfeld remembers: “I traveled to Tallinn to see art exhibitions, which seemed so Western-like and avant-garde for us in Leningrad, where it was almost impossible to exhibit openly what they were showing in Estonia.”⁵⁷ While the common rhetoric labeled the Balts as “Western,” in this context, the semantic difference between “Europe” and “the West” was irrelevant: Estonia as “Western” could only signify Western in European terms.

Estonians, for their part, shored up their national pride together with their European difference by juxtaposing themselves against the new Soviet-era settlers, whom they homogenized into a coherent entity they referred to as “Russians.” Estonian manners and habits were deemed superior, starting from the everyday basics: eating sunflowers seeds and spitting the shells carelessly about was held in disdain, the use of low-quality, strongly smelling cooking oil (as compared to relatively odorless margarine) was considered an inferior cultural practice. “Tuck your shirt in, son – you are not some kind of a Russian,” a man interviewed in 1993 remembers his grandmother saying. “At home it was always important to behave like a proper Estonian and not to shame oneself with behaving like a Russian,” this informant added.⁵⁸ Such everyday oppositions functioned as a decolonial reaction, a strategy for supporting communal self-respect.

⁵⁶ Elena Zubkova, *Pribaltika i Kreml’, 1940–1953* (Rosspen 2008) 3.

⁵⁷ Alla Rosenfeld, “Preface” in Alla Rosenfeld and Norton D Dodge (eds), *Art of the Baltics: The Struggle for Freedom of Artistic Expression Under the Soviets, 1945–1991* (Rutgers University Press and The Jane Voorhees Zimmerli Art Museum 2002) ix.

⁵⁸ Jaak Rakfeldt and Helle Rakfeldt-Leetmaa, “Rahvusliku identiteedi säilitamine okupeeritud Eestis” [1996] *Akadeemia* 1571, 1580.

Even during the era of Soviet censorship, oppositional motifs found their way into fiction, often through passing remarks or marginal characters. Characters such as Georgi Nikanorov in Teet Kallas's *Eiseni tänav* (*Eisen Street*, 1979) or Bobrin in Mats Traat's *Rippsild* (*Suspension Bridge*, 1980) are presented as simpletons compared to Estonians with their complex inner dilemmas. Bobrin gives a young Estonian couple an embarrassingly banal speech about the importance of making children: "Down with the pants and skirts, off with the bras and undershirts, out with the fake modesty – and then go at it!"⁵⁹ Nikanorov, the father of five children, encourages his former colleague Rein to follow a similar path: to beget children in order to get a new apartment with all the modern comforts in a Soviet suburb. Both Bobrin and Nikanorov are loud, robust, and simpleminded, not to be taken seriously. In *Rippsild* there is also a passing reference to an open conflict between different nationalities: when Kaida, a young Estonian woman, starts a relationship with a Russian-speaking man from Ukraine, Kaida's mother refuses to acknowledge their marriage and takes her daughter's child away to live with herself.

In Lilli Promet's novel *Primavera* (1971), the Estonian-Russian juxtaposition is developed in considerable detail. The main character, Saskia, an actress, provides a lengthy description of her everyday circumstances:

After a day's work, the crowded trams brought us home, women carrying heavy carrying shopping bags, filled with cooking oil, onions, bread, and cabbage.

The weekend started with joyous parties, but by Monday, plywood boards were fixed over broken windows and door panes.

I rode the tram with these non-local people every day or stood in line at the store – they didn't come to the theater. (15)

Pärast päevatööd töid täiskiilunud trammid meid koju, naistel käe otsas rasked kandevõrgud, enamasti ikka õli, sibulad, leib ja kapsad.

Nädalalõpp algas rõõmsate pidudega, aga esmaspäeval taoti lõhutud akna- või ukseklaaside asemele vineertahvlid ette.

⁵⁹ Mats Traat, *Rippsild* (Eesti Raamat 1979) 10.

Sõitsin selle mittepaigalise rahvaga iga päev ainult trammis koos või seisin
poejärjekorras, teatrisse nad ei tulnud. (15)

Greasy food, onions, cabbage, noisy parties sliding into destructive behavior, non-participation in cultural life, primitive modes of gender relations – one finds here a suggestive list of era-specific attributions externalized onto the image of the cultural Other: the unwanted, unwelcome new settler, whose growing presence was a continual marker of the colonial-style disregard for local interests.⁶⁰

Promet's *Primavera* offers a nearly perfect setting for considering the Europeanness of Estonians: the novel accompanies an Estonian actress on a Soviet tourist trip to Italy, where Saskia shares a hotel room with Fevronia, a woman from Russia.⁶¹ Slender Saskia enjoys the trip fully, orients herself easily in art museums, drinks wine in local cafes, attracts the interest of several male companions, and is mistaken for a German. Full-figured Fevronia, in contrast to Saskia, is clearly out of place in Italy: she displays ignorance and chauvinistic attitudes and is demanding and pretentious. Like the Italians, Saskia relies on strong coffee for energy, whereas Fevronia is upset when tea is unavailable. While Saskia and her attentive male companions enjoy Italian streetlife until late in the night, Fevronia gets lost because she is unable to read the Latin alphabet. In short, the novel emphasizes the Europeanness of the Estonian woman through her contrast with her markedly “less cultured” Russian roommate. The contrast between Saskia and Fevronia is so extreme that the Finnish reviewer Pekka Lilja had to cautiously admit, in his review of the Finnish translation in 1977, that Fevronia's character is presented in a such a grotesque light that it could “almost be considered racist.”⁶²

⁶⁰ Prior to the Soviet takeover, Estonia had been a relatively homogeneous nation-state, with the eponymous ethnicity making up 88.1 per cent of the population in 1934 and 97.3 per cent in 1945, after Hitler's *Umsiedlung* of the Baltic German population. By 1989, Estonian-speakers were reduced to 61.5 percent of the total, while in some regions Estonians had become a minority – a situation that for a nation of about one million caused anxieties of total assimilation. This data comes from Kalev Katus and Allan Puur, “Rahvastikuteadus ja Eesti rahvastikuarengu pöördepunktid” [2006] *Akadeemia* 491, 500; Annus, *Soviet Postcolonial Studies: A View from the Western Borderlands* (n 11) 45.

⁶¹ Lilli Promet and her husband Ralf Parve, writers loyal to the Soviet regime, traveled extensively and published several travelogues. *Primavera* is a fictionalized travelogue.

⁶² Pekka Lilja, “Lilli Prometi Itaalia-reis,” *Koos lahus. Uurimusi ja kriitikat eesti ja soome kirjandusest* (Tartu Ülikooli Kirjastus 2017) 228.

Pekka Lilja proposed that Promet's novel escaped serious imputation of racism by introducing another Russian, Konstantin, an intelligent and knowledgeable Russian professor, a researcher of classical culture.⁶³ Saskia's new Russian-speaking friends – a Jewish writer and the Russian professor – also accommodate themselves to the Italian setting with easy elegance, and they share Saskia's irritation with plump, ignorant Fevronia. In short, these two men, coming from Russia, are as European as Saskia is. Europeanness thus turns out to be correlated to categories of class and education: a Russian intellectual turns out to be no less European than his Estonian counterpart. The motif appears similarly in the novel *Rippsild*, where Dr Levin, whom an Estonian couple visits for treatment in Leningrad, is presented as both knowledgeable and desirable.

In a way, this corresponds to the Noor-Eesti mode of thinking: one becomes European by attuning oneself to European culture, through study and research, through choosing certain modes of creative self-expression. Europeanness is here understood as a category of aesthetics and knowledge. At the same time, the novel pokes fun of Fevronia's diligent note-taking – the assumption is that the necessary knowledge should *always already* have been acquired, and acquired somehow effortlessly and playfully. According to this formula, being European implies lightness, pleasure, and enjoyment, instead of a wrong-spirited scribbling of a guide's already oversimplified explanations – being European is characterized by a certain aesthetics of being, which the novel elaborates as an ontological positioning toward the surrounding world.

Promet's novel *Primavera* follows characters in exceptional circumstances – only very few from Soviet Estonia could enjoy leisure trips to Italy. The actress Saskia, likewise, has an exceptional profile: how many in the Estonian SSR would have displayed similar ease in recognizing and appreciating classical works of art? Yet thousands read Promet's novel, laughed at Fevronia and enjoyed the admiration that Saskia attracted on her fictional travels. The passive, non-dialogic Europeanness of a reader of fiction who faces not actual people in Italian streets and cafes, but instead follows words on the printed page and travels in an imaginary Europe from his or her cozy armchair – such armchair-Europeanness was secure from threats of

⁶³ In the Russian reception of the novel, the character of Konstantin did not neutralize the shocking presence of Fevronia. Promet's novel was translated and published in Russia, where it caused a considerable scandal. Johanna Ross, "Aira Kaalust Mari Saadini. Nõukogude Eesti naisarenguromaan ja selle lugemisviisid" (Tartu Ülikooli Kirjastus 2018) 132.

Orientalization and excluded the least hint of cultural discomfort. The novel's ambition, however, met with some indignities in its Finnish translation: the editor was obliged to correct many mistakes about Italy and its classical heritage.⁶⁴ But since rumors of Finnish editorial corrections would hardly reach Soviet Estonian audiences, Saskia's European success could be enjoyed domestically without critical disturbance.

In one of the 1976 issues of the cultural weekly *Sirp ja Vasar*, a group of Estonian elites shared their travel impressions after the trip to Canada and the USA. Among other general commentaries, the writer Enn Vetemaa observed casually: "For the European, Canada feels homier, both in terms of architecture and even in interpersonal relations. The United States feels inadvertently more foreign."⁶⁵ In the context of North America, Vetemaa easily identified with Europe. Even as the scale of Europe was in Soviet era significantly deactivated, the identification with Europe clearly survived in national imaginaries as embedded within the category of Estonianness.

From Soviet to post-Soviet: changes and continuities

The armchair-Europeanness that had been part of the Estonian self-image in the Soviet era was shaken up in the early 1990s, when the collapse of the Soviet Union brought about a rescaling of geopolitical realities and accompanying imaginaries. Transition-era political rhetoric foregrounded the vocabulary of a return: the emphasis was on the *re-establishment* of the independent state and *re-connecting* Estonia politically and economically with the rest of Europe and the world.⁶⁶ The discourse of restoration also implied a return to the nested scalar system "Estonia – Europe – the world" or, in the more detailed version, "Estonia – the Baltic sea region – Europe – the world." Yet in the 1990s, the dream of such safely nested belongingness could be realized only partially: the Soviet Union, albeit now dissolved, continued to loom over the new era with its continuing presence in global political imaginaries. What used to be the Soviet Union

⁶⁴ Lilja (n 63) 227.

⁶⁵ Maremäe (n 33) 4.

⁶⁶ Different varieties of such rhetoric were typical of this era also in other post-Socialist countries. Mikko Lagerspetz offers a comparative perspective in Mikko Lagerspetz, "Postsocialism as a Return: Notes on a Discursive Strategy" (1999) 13 *East European Politics and Societies* 377.

was now commonly referred to as “the former Soviet sphere,” and what used to be the Socialist bloc or the Soviet sphere of influence now became the so-called “post-socialist” countries.

Already from the late 1980s onward, Estonians and other non-Russian nationalities of the USSR had to struggle against the cultural erasure that had taken place during the past half century, when one geopolitical label – the Soviet Union – had obscured the great diversity within its imperial borders. Notes taken at the European Student Forum 1989 in Bologna are telling. Jüri Luik, who later made a name for himself as a distinguished politician, was then one of the two participating Estonian students and he commented on how Estonians had to contend with the perspective of the students from the EEC countries:

We structure the political map of the world to reflect ourselves as part of Europe. But looking from their vantage point, Europe ends on the eastern border of the Federal Republic of Germany. [...] From there we look like a province of Russia, a rebellious province that fights for some incomprehensible independence [...]

Of course, there are details that can impress. That you have a smart suit, that you have mastered the main European languages. In order to be equal, you have to be a little bit better.⁶⁷ (45)

Meie struktureerime maailma poliitilist kaarti nii, et loeme ennast Euroopa osaks. Sealtpoolt vaadates on Euroopa kõik see, mis lõpeb Saksa Liitvabariigi idapiiril. [...] Sealtpaistame me Venemaa provintsina, mässava provintsina, kes võitleb mingi mõistetamatu iseseisvuse eest [...]

On muidugi detaile, millega võid rabada. Et sul on viisakas ülikond, et sa oskad korralikult Euroopa kultuurkeeli. Selleks, et olla võrdne, pead olema veidike parem.

As Luik observes, the renewal of actual, two-way encounters led to the realization that there was a clear and uncomfortable mismatch between the Estonians’ sense of Europeanness and the EEC-countries’ more exclusive vision of Europe. Such a mismatch continued to be produced by way of labels such as “post-Soviet” or “post-socialist” – both implying a significant difference

⁶⁷ Jüri Luik, “Ühinevas Euroopas” [1989] Vikerkaar 37, 45.

from “real Europe.” The post-Soviet-era geographical imagination, like its Cold War predecessor reinforced the historical orientalizing of eastern Europe – the division of Europe into East and West – and judging the West as superior to the East⁶⁸ – but this was now newly strengthened by the dire need for Western investment in these societies undergoing transition.⁶⁹ While the rarity of direct interaction with countries outside the state-socialist bloc had neutralized the relevance of orientalizing visions during the Soviet Era, now new encounters with the orientalizing gaze of the “West” threatened Estonians’ internalized sense of Europeanness and created existential discomfort. The humiliating poverty of the years of transition exacerbated this unhappy situation.⁷⁰

For Estonia and other “post-Soviet” countries, the two simultaneous imaginary geographies – the aspirational “nested Europe” and the orientalizing binary judgment “post-Soviet East versus more advanced West” – clashed and intermingled in disconcerting ways. The imaginary of Europe, now again very concretely tied to geopolitical realities, also became divided into different institutional entities – in political terms, it was generally not “Europe,” but NATO, the Schengen area, the EEC and later the EU that was the locus of Estonia’s aspirational belonging. In the Soviet era, Europeanness had survived as a *cultural* marker of imaginary belongingness – now, for Estonian political elites, Europeanness became understood in terms of *economy*, *politics* and, importantly, *national security*. Marju Lauristin and Peeter Vihalemm summarize the priorities set at the beginning of Estonian transition as “economic competitiveness coupled with national security” – a combination that Lauristin and Vihalemm attested to be still

⁶⁸ Edward Said deployed the term ‘Orientalism’ to characterize the West’s strategies of encountering the Middle East. This concept has been likewise used to describe the West’s regard toward Eastern Europe. In this context, it is necessary to acknowledge the different conceptual coverage of the concepts “orientalism” and “colonialism”: while both terms indicate the relationship of subordination and othering, “colonialism” also involves the establishment of a specific sociopolitical system of subordination. Both involve a clearly hierarchical structure of scalarity, which is tied to questions of worth and value. Annus, ‘A Post-Soviet Eco-Digital Nation? Metonymic Processes of Nation-Building and Estonia’s High-Tech Dreams in the 2010s’ (n 8). See also Annus, *Soviet Postcolonial Studies: A View from the Western Borderlands* (n 10) 186.

⁶⁹ According to Larry Wolff, Orientalist associations with regards to Eastern Europe emerged in the Enlightenment era, when “the east of Europe” – in French *l’orient de l’Europe* – could easily be read as “the Orient of Europe.” Larry Wolff, *Inventing Eastern Europe: The Map of Civilization on the Mind of the Enlightenment* (Stanford University Press 1994) 6.

⁷⁰ Jüri Luik’s review of the 1989 European Student Forum also refers to the embarrassments in Bologna, when the invited Estonian students could not even afford to buy a cup of coffee Luik (n 68) 49.

in place in 2009, regardless of the deepening global economic crisis.⁷¹ Thus the former Soviet empire continued its presence in political imaginaries as a reminder of military threat, lending special urgency to Estonia's ambition to join European institutional and security frameworks.⁷²

In cultural imaginaries of the transition period, regained independence raised new questions about belonging – exactly how European are we? Actual encounters with the world outside the former Eastern bloc diminished the role played by Russia and Estonia's Russophone populations as cultural others – the role that formerly gave impetus to Estonians' imaginary sense of Europeaness during the Soviet era. The Noor-Eesti slogan "Let's be Estonians, but let's also become Europeans!" continued to be taught in schools, but, in a strongly future-oriented cultural era, its cultural relevance diminished. While in the Soviet-era the slogan had significant performative power, it now became part of national pedagogy, outside the active repertoire of cultural imagery.

The most widely discussed literary work of the 1990s period, the novel *Piiririik* (*The Border State*, 1993) by Emil Tode (a pen name for Tõnu Õnnepalu) was strongly marked by a sense of East-European Otherness. The main character of the novel, a gay man in Paris, feels both attraction and revulsion toward his new surroundings, with their Western consumer culture and sterile functionability. The main character's sense of non-belonging in Paris and yet his unwillingness to return lead him to an indefinable, liminal, border-state existence, and also to the realization that it is impossible to shake off one's past: past moods, colors, and landscapes continue to re-emerge in his thoughts regardless of geographic distance. While *Piiririik* was able to capture something important about its era, the 1990s cultural ferment escapes simple delineation – this era was characterized by great multiplicity, by a variety of hopes and aspirations, as a well as by bitter disappointments.

In Estonia, the economic crisis of the transition period was relatively shortlived: the national currency was successfully introduced in June 1992, and the economic situation started to improve already in early 1993. By September 1993, the president of the Estonian Bank judged

⁷¹ Lauristin and Vihalemm (n 15) 22.

⁷² Russian troops left Estonia only in August 1994, and especially during the period from 1992 to 1996, Russia was considered a direct threat to Estonia's security. According to the analysis provided by Erik Männik, by 1997, the Russian threat was regarded by Estonia as of secondary importance. Erik Männik, "Small States: Invited to NATO—Able to Contribute?" (2004) 20 *Defense & Security Analysis* 21, 27. 27

the crisis to be over.⁷³ In Lauristin's and Vihalemm's report, "According to World Bank analysis, Estonia in 1994 belonged to a group of countries that had [...] reached high levels of political freedom and economic stabilization."⁷⁴ Yet the restoration of national self-esteem and the feeling of collective agency vis-à-vis newly scaled geopolitical structures of the world required more time to develop. As with other former Eastern bloc countries, the judgmental, orientaling "Western gaze" complicated this process.

In time, Estonia's early 1990s crisis of collective agency developed into a story of collective success. By the 2010s, what had been an unstable post-colonial identity, defined by its struggle to come to terms with its Soviet heritage, had become overwritten by a new narrative gradually emerging: that of Estonia as the *eco-digital nation*,⁷⁵ a country and culture that cherishes and cares for its well-preserved natural habitats, while also moving at the forefront in digital technology.⁷⁶ Importantly, the ecodigital national narrative replaced the transition-era mismatch between the country's self-image as European and the orientaling gaze of the old imperial centers of the European West: the new narrative promoted the local sense of being, in certain respects, among the most successful in Europe and being appreciated as such. The culminating point in the new national narrative might be considered the 2017 EU digital summit in Tallinn, when, according to the *The New Yorker*, a speech by the President of Estonia Kersti Kaljulaid earned praise from the German chancellor, Angela Merkel: "You're so much further than we are."⁷⁷

⁷³ Sulev Vahtre (ed), *Eesti ajalugu VI. Vabadussõjast taasiseseisvumiseni* (Ilmamaa 2005) 403.

⁷⁴ Marju Lauristin and Peeter Vihalemm, "The Political Agenda During Different Periods of Estonian Transformation: External and Internal Factors" (2009) 40 *Journal of Baltic Studies* 1, 9.

⁷⁵ The eco-digital Estonia narrative is based on Estonia's actual success in the IT-sector by the 2010s, both in terms of public services and in terms of providing a flourishing start-up environment. According to the European Commission Country Report Estonia, 2019, "The country is a frontrunner as regards the digital provision of public services and has the highest proportion (96%) of e-Government users in Europe." Miroslav Beblavý and others, "Index of Readiness for Digital Lifelong Learning: Changing How Europeans Upgrade Their Skills" (2019).

⁷⁶ Annus, "A Post-Soviet Eco-Digital Nation? Metonymic Processes of Nation-Building and Estonia's High-Tech Dreams in the 2010s" (n 8). Note that this article also points to the selective or metonymic nature of such identity-formation.

⁷⁷ Nathan Heller, "Estonia - the Digital Republic" *The New Yorker* (December 11, 2017).

In the 2010s, being European had become a basic condition of life, the normal paradigm for being an Estonian. The formula for achieving this had already been articulated by Jüri Luik in 1989: “In order to be equal, you have to be a little bit better.”

Conclusion

As we have seen, Europeanness is a relational category, its role and its function in Estonian imaginaries are dependant on other identificatory categories active at the same period. “Europe” as an imaginary and as part of era-specific sociopolitical scalarity plays a different role in different eras: each era creates its own scalar logics, while activating certain geopolitical scales at the expense of others; in each era, cultural imaginaries rewrite geopolitical parametres through the lens of prior cultural experiences, thus forming competing imaginary geographies. These processes are accompanied by normative value-judgments which unavoidably enforce scalar hierarchies of higher and lower standings; secondary effects variously include feelings of superiority or otherness and processes of orientalization.

In the Soviet era Estonia, the Soviet colonial matrix of power disabled nation-level political agency and severed economic agency. However, while the Soviet leadership was able, within a period of a few years, to reorganize Estonian governmental structures, economy, and trade networks, the conservatism or inertia of processes of cultural identification made it impossible to switch the country into a full “Soviet” mode of cultural self-identification. The pre-Soviet decades of cultural development, including the Noor-Eesti call “Let’s be Estonians, but let’s also become Europeans!” continued to support Estonians’ sense of Europeanness. The rather insubstantial imaginary construction of such a mental framework could, however, find support in the continuing and visible presence of pre-Soviet material culture, architecture, natural environments, specific forms of cultural self-expression, and more. Continuing European standing on the cultural scale, however, gave some compensation for the enforced separation from Europe on the socioeconomic scale. Even as the Soviet colonial matrix of power worked to deactivate and downgrade the sociopolitical category of Europe, Europe continued its existence as an imagined, implicit quality Estonians could claim for themselves. The rarity of direct encounters neutralized the typically orientalizing gaze of Western Europeans toward East-Europeans; instead, Estonia’s position as “the Soviet West” within the USSR affirmed its imaginary belonging with Europe. As Savisaar’s speech suggested, the intense generation of new

ideas in the perestroika era heightened the local sense of agency – and to such an extent that Estonians could during this period self-identify as the avant-garde of the USSR.

Estonia emerged from the USSR with a strong sense of national agency and with a determined commitment to Europe. This strong, unquestioned sense of belonging to Europe, together with the continuing threat that Russia posed to national security, inspired the political leadership of the 1990s to prioritize an agenda of joining “all possible clubs”:⁷⁸ NATO, the Schengen area, the EEC and later the EU – an agenda that operated under the “logic of securitization”⁷⁹ to proceed with radical reforms that led to growing levels of inequality within the state, but that indeed found success in providing both security guarantees and a flourishing economic climate. The imaginary of Europe itself had changed substantially during this process, and changed from a predominantly aesthetic category to a predominantly geopolitical one.

In his 1992 speech *Estonia – Europe – the World*, Edgar Savisaar reflected on global future scenarios – among others, on the possibility of a Europe that has integrated Russia to become a global entity that stretched “from Gibraltar to the Urals” – a scenario that in the early 1990s did not sound utterly implausible.⁸⁰ Perhaps the biggest loss for Estonia in its re-joining of Europe has been the Putin-induced loss of St Petersburg as the most easily reachable European metropolis. Saskia, the actress from the novel *Primavera*, would have happily continued to walk its European streets in the company of her two friends, Russian intellectuals and Europeans like herself.

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⁷⁸ Mikko Lagerspetz and Henri Vogt, “Estonia” in Sten Berglund and others (eds), *The Handbook of Political Change in Eastern Europe. Third Edition* (Edward Elgar Publishing 2014) 55.

⁷⁹ *ibid* 67.

⁸⁰ Savisaar (n 3) 54.

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